

THE IMPORTANCE OF T. QAYPBERGENOV'S STORIES IN THE RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT OF THE KARAKALPAK PROSE

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If we look at the history of Karakalpak literature, the literature of the Karakalpak people began to develop for the first time as an oral folk art. The role of folk literature in the emergence of written literature is special. The genre of poetry developed very quickly in literature, literary representatives contributed to literature by creating poetic works. In particular, Jien bard, Kunkhozha, Azhiniyaz, Berdakh were famous as literary classics in the 19th century, and their work in promoting Karakalpak literature was high. The prose genre began to appear in Karakalpak literature from the 30s of the 20th century. However, prose did not immediately fall on the path of development. The reason is that the world war had a negative impact on the development of poetic works in literature. Writer M.Nurmuhammedov points out two main reasons for this situation: a) many prose writers went to the front; b) the demand for operatic genre increased during the war years. There was no time or personnel to study themes for novels with large-scale stories, to collect material, to write [1, p. 113].

In prose, the first examples of short stories and novels began to appear in the works of A. Shamuratov, N. Daukaraev, M. Daribaev, A. Begimov, J. Aymurzaev. The first stories written by writers became the basis for the emergence of prose in literature. Examples of folklore were evident in the early works of the authors. Legends, stories, and proverbs are usefully used from them.

In the 40s of the 20th century, A. Shamuratov's epic story became a big innovation in Karakalpak literature. The author was one of the first to create a lyric-epic story through his story «In the Old School». Q. Kamalov in his work «The Tale of Karakalpak»: «In our opinion, the national foundation of the lyric-epic story in the literature of Karakalpak begins with the lyric-epic epics. After that, the features of this type of genre were used as a national experience in A. Shamuratov's story «In the old school»[2, p. 38].

We fully agree with this opinion of the scientist. In the history of literature, an example of bringing this genre to a story can be seen in the story of the first writer. It was one of the important events for the period. A. Shamuratov tries to introduce examples of world literature into Karakalpak literature with his works. The work "My meetings with tigers" is proof of our word.

Here, H. Utemuratova's opinion on A. Shamuratov's story "In the Old School" attracted our attention: "A. Shamuratov's story also has certain flaws. From the point of view of this period, education in the old schools was criticized. In fact, the old schools and madrasahs provided education according to their times, and how many books were burned - this is the truth of history" [3, p. 18], she writes. H. Utemuratova's opinion is correct, because poets Azhiniyaz and Berdakh receive proper education in mosques and madrasahs. On the basis of the acquired knowledge, he brought new genres of poetry to literature. However, it is necessary to admit that writer A. Shamuratov brought something new to his story, and his skills in creating the plot, composition, and character of the hero are noteworthy.

The role of T. Qaypbergenov in the development of the story genre in Karakalpak literature is incomparable. The writer entered the literature with his stories, and then he began to write extensive literary works. The short story "Secretary" created in 1956 brought success to the writer. This was the writer's first step into the story genre. In the center of the story is Atamurat, the secretary of the school.

The themes of the artist's stories are wide in all respects. In the 50s of the 20th century, the writer's short story "Secretary" entered Karakalpak literature.

Atamurat is a secretary, a brave young man of the village. During the Second World War, most of the elders of the village left for the war, and the fate of the village people was left to the youth. Atamurat doesn't care about being young, he keeps himself strong and starts hard work in front of the village people.

At the beginning of the 20th century, it became popular to show the depiction of rural life in literature. When revealing the theme, the image of workers, a rich and a poor farmer was depicted in a contrasting form, and concepts of positive or negative heroes began to be used. By describing the behavior of people of different ages while revealing real life, all the characters in the story serve to reveal the image of the main character.

The story is written about the life of villagers and the fate of schoolchildren during the war years. Atamurat works tirelessly for the rural people. With his exemplary behavior, he takes a positive place in the hearts of librarians. Other characters in the story serve to reveal Atamurat's character. The plot of the work is simple, lightly written. The story describes the negative actions of Atakhan, a refugee who fled the war. Atakhan is a war refugee and a bad person. At the beginning of the story, it is said: "Early in the morning, three children

returning from the city, unable to sit on the ground because of the cold, are driving with their donkeys in front of them." At the beginning of the story, it is described that three children are coming to the village in this way. These young children are Atamurat, Amet and Serjan, who are accompanying their loved ones to the World War. These three children are different in age and lifestyle. Atamurat is the son of Jumamurat, a village tractor driver. Amet is the son of Atakhan, the head of the farm in the 7th of November collective farm, and the third is the son of Aygul, a widow in the village.

The story, written in an epic genre, describes the heroism of a young boy during the war. Scientist Q. Kamalov defines the image of Atamurat as follows:

Atamurat is Timur of Karakalpak. He is an active student. Secretary of the Komsomol school committee. Delivering letters from the front to parents, talking about disorderly people, helping collective farmers, encouraging schoolchildren to rest, and helping refugees fleeing from the front - all of these actions are similar to Atamurat's image of Timur. (Timur - the famous Russian Soviet magician Arkady Gaidar's «Timur is the main character of the story "his team" [2, p. 62].

Atamurat is the village hero described above. With his behavior as an example to the youth of his time, he stood out for his bravery behind the front during the Second World War. Even today, there are no such demanding young people in our time. Serving the country has become a duty for every young man. Father Temirkhan, Amet, Serjan, Zibayda, Kalbay try with all their might to reveal the character of Atamurat in the story. The fact that Temirkhan ata, despite being one of the elders in the village, knew Atamurat as a teacher and respected him is considered an example of humane qualities in the true sense for today's youth and adults.

When considering the direction of development of prose in Karakalpak literature, after the 50s of the 20th century, the theme of the World War began to be widely described in prose. The sad consequences of the war, the hard work of the people behind the front lines, and the fate of the refugees who fled the war can be seen in the works of this period. This has become one of the important topics not only in Karakalpak literature, but also in world literature.

During this period, T. Qaypbergenov also extensively described the subject of such a war in his stories. Studying the writer's works on such a theme, it is worth noting the works of other writers. In the last years after the war, there have been a lot of works in Karakalpak literature that embody the war period.

Written works were created by the skill of the authors in creating images. There are also close characters between them.

There are many exemplary aspects of the writer who created in this way during the period when the prose genre was mixed with literature. Ch. Aitmatov's ideas in his stories and novels, a well-known representative of world literature in the 20th century, are similar to T. Qaypbergenov's. The reason is that the content, images, and characters of each created work do not completely repeat each other, but it is possible to clearly see the repetition of some elements in it. Comparing the works of writers, it is a mistake to think that their works repeat each other. The creation of works based on the problems demanded by the era was important in every nation.

The refugee image of Ismail in Ch. Aitmatov's novel "Face to face" is very close to the image of the refugee in T. Qaypbergenov's story "Secretary".

In the story of the writer T. Qaypbergenov: "He fell ill today to perform his next task." But this time he decided to see his father face to face" [4, p. 319]. Face to face is not just a word, looking into the eyes of a refugee father, knowing that he is a bad person is very difficult for a child. Amet has not visited his father for the first time today, he will hear from him as soon as possible. She brings him bread and extra food. Ch. Aitmatov's work based on this idea is called "Face to Face". He is also a refugee who is afraid to face the villagers and his relatives.

In this place, the novel "Aqdarya" by the writer K. Sultanov, who is known for his valuable work in Karakalpak literature, comes to our eyes. In the plot of the novel, a character who is angry with the people is depicted as a refugee. In the novel depicting the war period, the writer describes his life before the war, what he did and the period before he was called to the war, while creating the character of the refugee. In the novel, the image of Qadir the refugee is created very skillfully, his image, which has become a wild creature, not a human being, arouses anger in a person. The images of Atakhan, Ismail and Qadir are very close to each other, similar images.

Their character, appearance, and deeds are close to each other. However, it is a mistake to think that the works of writers have repeated each other and that the ideas inside are completely the same. Writers' skills in choosing a plot, compositional features, narrative skills and styles in revealing character are completely different from each other. Only one character in the works is depicted close to each other.

We agree with the opinion of literary critic and scientist J. Esenov: "T. Qaypbergenov and Sh. Aytmatov did not create works influenced by each other,

both of them created at the same time"[5, p. 66]. The reason is that the authors of the above compared works are known to be great writers of their time. The images and characters created by them are important in the development of literature.

Bringing the image of a new teacher to literature at the end of the 50s of the 20th century, it shows that the works of the writer who received the state award named "Hamza" are valuable. The education and upbringing of village children by a teacher from the village is skillfully described. The title of the story is also well thought out. The above points are made about the story depicting the old-fashioned education of children during the former Soviet Union. The idea, theme, and narrative skills of the story "Thanks to the Teacher" written in the lyrical-epic style were completely different from A. Shamuratov's work. The history of the inhabitants of the village of "Dóngelek kól", their level of thinking and thinking are skillfully described in the story. The story is told in the language of the hero Turdimurat. Despite the fact that Turdimurat is a young boy, Menlimurat serves positively to the growth of the village people's thinking and the introduction of a new life by performing the role of teacher's assistant. The idea of storytelling is also important for today's youth. In the mentioned period, it is described that parents and village elders refused to send their children to a teacher for education. In today's time, it is the opposite, the teacher is not looking for the children, but the students and their parents are trying to learn by looking for the teacher. The story is based on a topical theme for the time it was created. If this story were created in today's information technology age, it would be unreliable.

A short time after Menlimurat's teacher entered Karakalpak literature, Duyshen, the first teacher of Academician Altinay Sulaymanova, entered Kyrgyz literature. Duyshen teacher, created by Ch. Aytmatov, uses the method of imparting new knowledge from the old era, advocates the same experience of women as men, and calls on young people to learn. The ideas of the stories are written close to each other. However, the characters of the created image are different from each other. In the story created by T. Qaypbergenov, the image of Duysen Molla is widely revealed. He was the mullah of the village, who tried to make the people literate by teaching children in the old fashion before the teacher came.

Some of his views and thinking were narrow. It was Duysen Molla who had a negative opinion of Menlimurat teacher. Duyshen, the character created by

Ch.Aytmatov, saves the people from the old way of thinking and introduces a new method of education to the village.

The work of T. Qaypbergenov played a special role in the evolution of the storyteller's research and the emergence of the lyric-psychological story. Through the stories "Cold Drop", "Sleepless Nights", the writer introduced a new direction of the story genre to Karakalpak literature. The skillful description of the human heart full of emotions, which has a strong influence on human psychology, proves that the writer has a special place in the field of literature.

Kamal, Gulzar Karakalpakova, these characters are no stranger to reading books.

Both characters are adults. Those who faced hardships from their youth and faced the dark days of life no matter how many hard days passed and achieved good days like the sun. In his short story "Cold Drop", T. Qaypbergenov skillfully describes the character of Kamal, a young boy psychologically crushed by the reason of his traitorous father. Unable to bear the shame, a young boy commits suicide and stabs himself in the stomach. But his mother, Guljan, explains that it is wrong to die from such hardships of life. The plot of the story begins with the writer's acquaintance with Kamal in the bathroom, and a cold drop that falls on the writer's head causes his whole body to shiver. The incident is narrated in Kamal's language from the diary.

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